

RESEARCH ARTICLE

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FINANCIAL LEVERAGE AND FINANCIAL STABILITY OF QUOTED INDUSTRIAL GOODS FIRMS IN NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

Businesses use financing decisions to optimize their capital structure, control risk, and spur growth. In view of this, this study examined the relationship between financial leverage and financial stability of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to determine the effect of debt-equity ratio on liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria, to ascertain the effect of interest coverage ratio on liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria and to assess the effect of total debt ratio on liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Ex-post facto research design was adopted, and panel data covering ten (10) years (2014-2023) were collected from twelve (12) listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria which formed the sample size of the study. The data collected were analysed using panel linear regression technique. Findings showed that debt equity ratio has a significant negative relationship (Coeff. = -0.00219{0.0097}) with liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria while interest coverage ratio has a significant positive relationship (Coeff. = 0.00029{0.0124}) with liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria. It also revealed that total debt ratio has a non-significant negative relationship (Coeff. = -0.00011{0.1260}) with liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria. It was thus concluded that financial leverage has a significant impact on the financial stability of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Recommendations made included that quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria should consider reducing their debt levels and increasing their equity base. This could be achieved through strategies such as debt restructuring, equity financing, and improving profitability to reduce dependence on debt.

INTRODUCTION

Financing choices are crucial for companies looking for ways to out weight competition in today's intensely competitive and interconnected worldwide marketplace. Nigeria's economy is no exception when it comes to the industrial goods sector, which stimulates growth, innovation, and job creation. Businesses use financing decisions to optimize their capital structure, control risk, and spur growth. These choices include figuring out the best amount of leverage, deciding between short- and long-term financing solutions, and picking the appropriate ratio of debt to equity. Samuel and Yahaya, (2024) stipulates that poor finance choices are a ticking time bomb that might have a catastrophic effect on businesses, plunging them into a maze of financial instability and protracted stagnation. According to Brealey et al. (2020), this implies that there is a lack of equity basis, high debt levels, an unbalanced debt-to-equity ratio, and an excessive amount of short-term debt. These factors raise financial risk and enhance the possibility of default and liquidity crises. These consequences include higher likelihood of default, bankruptcy, or financial distress, downgrade in credit rating (Kisgen, 2006), increased cost of debt and equity (Ross et al., 2019), reduced profitability, and reduced share price, dividend payments, and overall returns. As such, firms need to maintain an optimal capital structure to ensure financial flexibility, reduce risk, and maximize financial stability.

However, achieving an optimal capital structure is challenging, and companies must balance debt and equity to respond to changing market conditions, fund new projects, and maintain control over their operations as argued by Modigliani and Miller (1958). Financial leverage is a measure of how much firm uses equity and debt to finance its assets. As debt increases, financial leverage increases. A firm is considered leveraged when the firm is partially financed by both debt and equity. Most firms survive with a significant liquidity level which is mainly achievable through use of debt. Many companies use debt to leverage their profits and capital. It relates to splitting finance into debt and equity elements with each of these having its peculiar features, merits and demerits on firm sustainability and market value. Debt bears a fixed cost. This means that when a firm increases its debt level, the financial leverage level increases. Leverage is the use of borrowed funds for investment purposes (Dinh& Pham, 2020). When a firm's management increases the firm's profit by using debt elements, it is an indication of quality corporate governance. A firm's investments can be financed by the use of either debt or equity. When a firm uses fixed-charged funds especially preference capital and debt along with the shareholder's equity this is referred to as financial leverage or gearing. When a company's capital structure is made of only shareholders 'or owners' equity only it's said to be unlevered firm whereas when a firm's capital structure is made of both debt and owners' equity it is said to be levered (Guner, 2016).

A business entity is said to be financially stable when it is capable of efficiently allocating resources, assessing and managing financial risks, maintaining employment levels close to the economy's natural rate, and eliminating relative price movements of real or financial assets that will affect monetary stability or employment levels (Samuel &Yahaya, 2024). Also, a firm is in a range of stability when it dissipates financial imbalances that arise endogenously or as a result of significant adverse and unforeseen events. In stability, the firm absorbs the shocks primarily via self-corrective mechanisms, preventing adverse events from having a disruptive effect on the going concern of the business. The industrial goods sector consists of the companies that produce and sell capital goods to other businesses. In contrast to the consumer goods sector that produces goods and services directly consumed by households, the industrial goods sector provides capital goods to other businesses for manufacturing and construction. The sub-sectors include aerospace and defence, homebuilding, electric equipment, machinery, construction and engineering, distributors, etc.

Most businesses in the industrial goods sector are sensitive to the economic cycle. The industrial goods sector has high barriers of entry due to large capital investments and cost-saving from economies of scale. However, with a wide range of sub-sectors, not all businesses in the sector slow down their production simultaneously. Some sub-sectors may lag, while some may lead the economic cycles. Waste management companies and industrial conglomerates often demonstrate resilience. They are able to generate relatively steady revenue streams during economic downturns.

Statement of the Problem

Financial decision-making is a critical aspect of corporate finance, as it significantly impacts a firm's survival, performance, and overall success. Capital, or finance, is a vital resource that drives financial decision-making, and companies can source it internally through retained earnings, depreciation, tax shields, and other non-cash transactions, or externally through debt and/or equity financing (Amahalu, et al. 2018). A highly leveraged company, property, or investment is characterized by having more debt than equity, indicating a higher level of financial risk. Both investors and companies utilize the concept of leverage to amplify potential returns, with investors leveraging their investments using various financial instruments, such as options, futures, and margin accounts, and companies using leverage to finance their operations, investments, and growth initiatives. The use of leverage, however, involves a delicate balance between the benefits of increased returns and the risks of heightened debt levels. Where a business firm uses more debt than equity in its capital structure, it incurs a greater portion of fixed costs (interest payments) and enjoys tax waivers. At the same time, leverage also multiplies the potential downside risk where the investment does not yield the expected returns. Moreover, many firms are eager to pay off their debts quickly by adopting debt-reduction methods that add risks and may negatively affect their cash flows.

While financial leverage is recognized as a crucial factor in understanding firm liquidity (Senan et al., 2021; Okeke et al., 2021) and financing decisions (Subhani et al., 2022), a notable gap exists in the literature regarding the moderating effect of firm size on the relationship between financing decisions and financial stability. Only a few studies have explored this moderating effect (Vengesai, 2023; Setianti&Haryono, 2023), highlighting the need for further research to examine how firm size influences the impact of financial leverage on financial stability and to investigate differences in financing decisions and financial stability across firms of varying sizes. The inconclusive results and lack of consensus in the reviewed literature gave rise to a gap in literature that this study aims to address.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to ascertain the relationship between financial leverage and financial stability of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

1. Determine the relationship between debt-equity ratio and liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria.
2. Ascertain the relationship between interest coverage ratio and liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria.
3. Appraise the relationship between total debt ratio and liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

Research Questions

This study sought to provide reliable answers to the following questions;

1. What is the effect of debt-equity ratio on liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria?
2. To what extent does interest coverage ratio affect liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria?
3. How does total debt ratio affect liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses as stated in their null form were adopted for the study;

- H01:** There is no significant relationship between debt-equity ratio and liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria
- H02:** There is no significant relationship between interest coverage ratio and liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria
- H03:** There is no significant relationship between total debt ratio and liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria

Scope of the Study

Content scope: The explanatory variables for financial leverage were debt-equity ratio, interest coverage ratio and total debt ratio. Liquidity was however used as the proxy for the dependent variable (financial stability).

Geographical scope: The study covers a period of 10 years, from 2014 to 2023, examining the relationship that exists between financial leverage and stability of quoted industrial good firms in Nigeria.

Unit scope: The study was limited to 12 industrial goods firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group, which are the units of analysis.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher's Conceptualization, (2025).

The Concept of Financial Leverage

Financial leverage is a measure of the use of debt versus the use of equity to finance the assets and activities of an organization (Audax, 2018). It is one of the financing decisions that firms have to make. If the funds are not paid back as agreed, the financier can commence collection proceedings (Enekwe, *et al.* 2014). Debt financing is mainly in the form of loan and bond but other form such as securing goods on credit also exist (Akayi et al, 2021). High usage of debt financing leads to an increase in financial leverage and is associated with greater risk of bankruptcy. However, it is also associated with various advantages such as maintaining company ownership intact, tax deductions, and low transactional costs (Mboi, *et al.* 2018). On the other hand, equity financing entails raising money by selling of company shares to investors who acquire ownership in the company (Audax, 2018). Equity financing may also come in the form of reinvesting the company's profits.

The cost of equity is usually the claim on earnings provided to shareholders for their ownership stake (Edore&Ujuju, 2020). Although equity financing is associated with lower risks of bankruptcy, it is an expensive source of financing as investor demand a higher rate of return (Ahmadu, 2021). Companies can use leverage to finance their assets; instead of issuing stock to raise capital, companies can use debt financing to invest in business operations in an attempt to increase shareholder value (Kenton, 2021). The financial leverage of a company depends on the choice made by the management to either use debt or equity to fund the operations of the company. Financial leverage is often gauged using the debt ratio, equity ratio, and debt to equity ratio (Enekwe, *et al.*, 2014).

Variables of Financial Leverage

Debt-Equity Ratio

The debt-equity ratio is a leverage ratio that calculates the weight of total debt and financial liabilities against total shareholders' equity. It indicates the relative proportion of shareholders' equity and debt used to finance a company's assets (Okoye, *et al.*2016). The debt-to-equity ratio is a financial as well as liquidity ratio that compares a company's total debt to total equity (Enekwe *et al.*, 2014). The debt-to-equity ratio shows the percentage of company financing that comes from creditors and investors as highlighted by Gunarathna (2016). It is often expressed in percentage as shown below;

$$\text{Debt-equity ratio} = \frac{\text{Totaldebt}}{\text{Equity share+reserve}} \times 100$$

A higher total debt-to-equity ratio indicates that the sector has been increasing the relative share of debt in external financing, whereas a lower debt-to-equity ratio indicates that the sector is financing a decreasing proportion of its activities through debt as compared to financing through their equity (retained earnings and net new share issuance) as stressed by Ofuleet *al.*, (2022). According to Okekeet *al.*; (2021), higher debt levels result in volatile earnings due to additional interest expense as well as increased vulnerability to business downturns. The debt-to-equity ratio shows the proportions of equity and debt a company is using to finance its assets and it signals the extent to which shareholder's equity can fulfil obligations to creditors, in the event a business declines (Andrew, 2021)

Interest Cover Ratio

This ratio is commonly referred to as "times interest earned". It does not take into consideration the principal debt repayment (Hassan&Adegbie, 2021). It is concerned with

payment of accumulated interest only. This ratio measures the number of times an entity's operating profit can pay off the entity's interest expense as highlighted by Okekeet *al.*, (2021). As stressed by Ofuleet *al.* (2022). Many industrial goods firms face the challenge of covering interest liabilities continuously. Hence, it is essential for solvency and liquidity to secure these liabilities with a revenue stream. Thomas and Zechner, (2021) observed that when a company is having trouble meeting its obligations, it may have to borrow more or utilize its cash reserve but should regularly consider the ability of the firm to generate income that can offset the interest payments. Such cash reserves would be better spent on capital assets or to meet contingencies. Interest cover ratio is calculated as;

$$\text{Interest cover ratio} = \frac{\text{Profit before interest and tax}}{\text{interest charges}}$$

This ratio is useful to understand a company's capability or financial strength to pay its debt interest. A higher ratio is better because it shows that the company is making enough profit to settle its interest expense and is a sign of financial strength for the company. Also, the higher the ratio, the higher the level of confidence of lenders in the ability of the company to repay loans granted to it. Koriret *al.*, (2022) observed that interest payments have an impact on financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Kenya.

Total Debt Ratio

Total debt ratio is a financial ratio that indicates the percentage of a company's assets that are provided via debt. It is the ratio of total debt (short-term and long-term liabilities) and total assets (Pachori & Totala, 2012). Total debt measures the proportion of the business assets financed with debts and in effect also measures the degree of protection to unsecured creditors in the event of liquidation (Umar & AbdulQudus, 2020). Adenugba, *et al.* (2016) argued that it is a measure of business' financial risk, the risk that the firm's total assets may not be sufficient to pay off its debts and interest thereon. Debt could be attained in many different ways, and another common way of categorizing debt is based on its different maturities (Ofuleet *al.*, 2022). There are short-term debt, long-term debt and convertible debt. Short-term debt is defined as payments due within one year and is found under current liabilities on the statement of financial position (Umar & AbdulQudus, 2020). This could be short-term bank loans, but also longer-term loans that are due within one year, as well as other outstanding debt maturing within a year. Total debt ratio is calculated as;

$$\text{Total debt ratio} = \frac{\text{Current liabilities + longterm loans}}{\text{Total assets}}$$

Mboi, *et al.* (2018) argued that total debt ratio is very important in determining the risk of default and bankruptcy faced by a firm, as it will affect the choice of capital structure (Lawalet *al.*, 2014). When determining a firm's financial health, the current liability account should not exceed the amount of cash and cash equivalents available in the firm, since this will mean that the firm cannot meet its current obligations (Ezejioforet *al.*, 2029).

Concept of Financial Stability

Financial stability is the ability to withstand a temporary problem, such as a decrease in sales, lack of capital or loss of a key employee or customer (Hassan & Adegbe, 2021). As such, stable firms have higher cash flows caused by stable revenue and expense patterns with lower reinvestment needs as argued by Okekeet *al.* (2021). This makes them attractive borrowers as they can repay the loans and honour the interest payment obligations in time. Further, stable firms have a compulsion to reduce their cost of equity and therefore their debt-equity ratio is normally high. Financial stability is paramount for firm's growth as most investment

portfolios in the real economy can be well appraised by the firm (Okeke, *et al.* 2021). Financial stability ratios are tools for gauging ability to meet long-term obligations with enough working capital left to operate.

The main determinant of financial stability is liquidity and it was used in measuring the effect of financial stability on financial leverage.

Theoretical Framework

The Trade-off theory (Kraus and Litzenberger,1973)

Kraus and Litzenberger (1973) proposed the Trade-off Theory. According to Murray and Goyal (2017), the traditional Trade-off theory or the tax Shield- Bankruptcy cost theory postulates that the value of a firm may be maximized at an optimal level of capital structure where the marginal benefits of debt (that is, the present value of tax savings from tax deductibility of interest payments) and the marginal costs of debt (that is, the present value of potential bankruptcy costs, holding its assets and investment plans constant) are equalized. The trade-off theory has become the most acceptable theory to explain financial leverage in recent time. Trade-off theory actually supports leverage in constructing capital structure by assuming leverage benefits. Optimal level of leverage is achieved by balancing the benefits from interest payments and costs of debt. Financially, debt is considered beneficial because of the debt-tax-shields that help to minimize expected tax bills and maximize the after-tax cash flows (Watts & Zimmerman, 2013). Trade-off theory hence predicts the cost and benefit analysis of debt financing to achieve optimal capital structure.

The Trade-off theory states that the optimal capital structure at which a company value is maximized to a target debt ratio can be obtained through establishing a trade-off between tax and other benefits against financial distress and other costs resulted from issuing debt (Matermilola&Bany-Ariffin, 2011). Although debt can offer a tax shield, it raises the probability of bankruptcy. As the level of debt increases, both tax shield and bankruptcy risk will increase. Additionally, through comparing tax benefits of debt and costs of bankruptcy, the Trade-off theory shows a positive relationship between debt and firms stability until the optimal point where the cost brought by financial distress equals the benefits earned from tax saving. Considering this, when a firm plans to maximize its value and compare the amount of debt and equity to use, it is supposed to pay attention on the trade-off between the benefits of tax shield and the cost of financial distress. (Dissanayake, 2018).The Tradeoff theory expects long term debt to positively impact firms' stability because companies that have higher stability ratios are less risky to debt holders and have more debt capacity.

Empirical Framework

Ofulue, *et al.* (2022) studied the relationship between financial leverage and financial performance of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria for a thirteen (13) year period covering from 2008-2020. It concluded that Short-term debt ratio significantly and positively relates with the cash value-added while Debt-equity Ratio and Long-term debt ratio have a significant negative relationship.

Akayi, *et al.* (2021) examined the effect of debt-equity financing on firm's performance in Nigeria using a sample of 26 firms randomly selected from oil and gas, Health care and ICT sectors of the Nigerian stock exchange for the period from year 2013 to 2020. Ordinary least square regression model was however used and the findings of the study revealed that Debt financing has significant and positive effect on firm performance in Nigeria at 5% level of

significance. It was however recommended that firms should try to finance their investment activities with debt and equity to consider either debt or equity as a last option.

Hassan and Adegbe (2021) examined the effect of financial leverage on cash flow of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Thirteen (13) listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria from 2009 to 2018 were studied using ex-post facto research design. One of the major findings from this empirical analysis is that financial leverage has significant effect on cash flow of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Odumet *al.* (2021) examined the effect of financial leverage on financial performance of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria over the period of 2009-2020. A sample of 14 Industrial goods firms was selected. Multiple regression technique was however adopted for analysis of data. The study findings revealed that short-term debt ratio significantly and positively relates with the cash value-added while debt-equity ratio and long-term debt ratio have a significant negative relationship.

METHODOLOGY

This section focused on the methods and procedures used in collecting and analysing data for the study (Attih, 2024; Attih et al., 2023; Essien et al., 2023). It consists of research design, population of the study, sample size and sample size determination, sampling technique, sources of data and method of data collection, method of data analysis, model specification, and measurement and operationalization of variables.

Research Design

This work adopted an *ex-post facto* research design. This was because it establishes a cause-effect relationship and the researcher had no control over the variables under study. This design is very appropriate where it is not possible for the researcher to directly manipulate the independent variable.

Population of the Study

According to Eke and Udonde (2023), population is the totality of all elements (human and material) being studied. The population of this study comprised of 13 industrial goods firms quoted on the floor of the Nigerian Stock Exchange as at the end of year 2023. Also, availability of data served as the yardstick for selection. Industrial goods firms that were continuously listed by Nigeria stock exchange during the period (2014 -2023) and whose financial statements and reports are available and have been consistently submitted to Nigeria stock exchange for the period under study were selected. These industrial goods firms are as shown in table 3.1 below;

Table 3.1: List of Quoted Industrial Goods Firms in Nigeria as at 2023

S/N.	Company Name	Ticker
1	Austin Laz & Co. PLC	AUSTIN LAZ
2	Berger Paints PLC	B E R G E R
3	BETA Glass PLC	BETAGLAS
4	BUA Cement PLC	BUACEMENT
5	C A P P L C	C A P

6	C u t i x P L C	C U T I X
7	Dangote Cement PLC	D A N G C E M
8	Grief Nigeria PLC	V A N L E E R
9	Laferge Africa PLC	W A P C O
1 0	Notore Chemicals PLC	N O T O R E
1 1	Premier Paints PLC	P R E M P A I N T S
1 2	M e y e r P L C	M E Y E R
1 3	Tripple Gee & Co. PLC	T R I P P L E G

Source: Researcher's Compilation, (2025).

Sample Size and Sample Size Determination

In the course of this study, the population also served as the sample size. This is because the population was manageable enough for the researcher to handle and obtain all required data necessary for the study. Therefore, 12 out of 13 quoted Industrial goods firms formed the sample of the study. That is, all the firms in the population were studied exception of Austin Laz & Co. Plc.

Sampling Technique

Complete enumeration also known as census sampling technique was used to obtain the data for the study. According to Udonde, Akpan and Awah (2021), complete enumeration is used when the assembled sample has the same proportion of individuals as the entire population.

That means $n=N$

Where;

n = sample size and N = population

Sources of Data and Method of Data Collection

The data for the dependent and independent variables were extracted from financial reports using contents analysis method and collated with the aid of Microsoft excel software. The panel data methodology was adopted because the study combined time series and cross-sectional data that is twelve (12) cross-sectional observations for each year and ten-time series for each industrial goods firm regressor and explained variables, a total of one hundred and twenty (120) pooled observations. A panel data set has multiple entities each of which has repeated measurements at different time periods. Panel data give more informative data, more degrees of freedom and more efficiency. They also provide ways of dealing with diverse data and examine fixed and random effects on the longitudinal data.

Method of Data Analysis

The study adopted multiple regression (Ordinary Least Square-OLS) analysis to analyse data via Eviews 10.0. The data conformed to the standardized linear regression assumptions, that is, linearity, homoscedasticity, normality and independence of data. Durbin Watson statistics is within the range of 1-3, (Gujarati et al., 2012; Kothari, & Gaurav, 2014; Tabachnick&Fidell, 2007).

Model Specification

To achieve the stated objectives of the study, as well as testing the study hypotheses, a multiple linear regression model was adopted. Hence, the broad model for this study is as presented below;

$$LIQ_{it} = f(DER, ICR, TDR)$$

$$LIQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DER_{it} + \beta_2 ICR_{it} + \beta_3 TDR_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

Where;

- LIQ = Liquidity measured using Cash ratio
- DER = Debt equity ratio
- ICR = Interest coverage ratio
- TDR = Total debt ratio
- β_0 = Intercept or regression constant
- $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = Regression coefficient;
- μ = Stochastic error term.

Measurement and operationalization of variables

Table 3.2 Operationalization of variables

C o n c e p t	P r o x y	M e a s u r e m e n t	S o u r c e
(Independent variable)	Financial leverage	Debt equity ratio	It is measured by dividing total debt by total equity and reserve in a any reporting period.
		Interest coverage ratio	It is measured by dividing profit before interest and tax by total interest charges.
		Total debt ratio	It is measured by dividing total debts by total assets owned and used in the course of operation.
S t a b i l i t y	L i q u i d i t y	It is measured by dividing total cash and cash equivalents by total current liabilities.	Okoye, et al.(2016). Korir, et al.(2022) Mboi, et al. (2018). Ofule, et al. (2022), Stapleton (2021)
(Dependent variable)			

Source:Researcher’s Compilation, (2025).

Decision Rule

The decision was based on 5% level of significance. Accept null hypothesis (H0) if probability value (i.e. P-value or Sig.) is greater than or equals to (\geq) stated 5% level of

significance (α); otherwise, reject and accept alternate hypothesis (H_a), if p-value or sig calculated is less than 5% level of significance.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Data Presentation

The dataset comprises a panel data of one hundred and twenty (120) observations across twelve (12) quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria for ten (10) years (2014-2023). The data include the dependent variable -Cash Ratio of quoted industrial goods firms (CashR) and the independent variables which include Debt-Equity Ratio of quoted industrial goods firms (DER), Interest Cover Ratio of quoted industrial goods firms (ICR), and Total Debt Ratio of quoted industrial goods firms (TDR).

Data Analysis

Various statistical techniques were utilized in the analysis of data. These include descriptive statistic technique and panel multiple regression technique. The results from the panel regression method were used in the testing of the research hypotheses which have been stated in the first chapter of this work.

1. Descriptive statistics of industrial goods firms' financial ratios.

This was conducted to understand the behaviour of the data using various statistics including mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis. The result for the descriptive statistics analysis of Nigerian quoted industrial goods firms' financial ratios for the period of ten years (i.e. 2014-2023) as presented in Table 4.1

Table 4.1: Descriptive statistics results

	C	A	S	H	R	D	E	R	I	C	R	T	D	R
Mean	0.3794	120.8037	8315.6518	20.4461	118									
Median	0.2989	140.7424	4213.1527	770.4883	304									
Maximum	2.9601	14510.4667	247.4739	52.2296	56									
Minimum	-1.0626	64-179.4374	-1659.523	-4.8920	60									
Std. Dev.	0.4732	1116.9859	3167.3878	0.5644	54									
Skewness	1.4194	67-9.8948	08-8.2939	93-6.8435	62									
Kurtosis	9.7312	66103.8155	78.2112	868.7163	2									
Jarque-Bera	266.8475	52776.96	29659.49	22529.86										
Probability	0.0863	400.0263	4890.0883	470.0742	60									
Sum	45.5294	8-96.4539	8-3078.218	53.5341	6									
Sum Sq. Dev.	26.6475	234334.11	3334223.37	91435										
Observations	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	2

Source: Researcher's computation (2025) using E-views 10.0

The table shows that cash ratio (CashR), Debt-Equity Ratio (DER), Interest Cover Ratio (ICR) and Total Debt Ratio (TDR) of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria had mean values of approximately 0.3794, 0.8037 (or 80.37%), 15.65 times and 0.4461 (or 44.61%) respectively. This indicates the central or average values for these variables from 2014 to 2023. The median values obtained for cash ratio (CashR), Debt-Equity Ratio (DER), Interest Cover Ratio (ICR) and Total Debt Ratio (TDR) of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria were approximately 0.2989, 0.7424 (or 74.24%), 13.15 times and 0.4883 (or 48.83%) respectively. These constitute the middle values for the distributions of these variables under the period covered in this study (2014-2023).

In terms of the level of variability and dispersion in the distribution of these variables, the standard deviations obtained for cash ratio (CashR), Debt-Equity Ratio (DER), Interest Cover Ratio (ICR) and Total Debt Ratio (TDR) of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria were 0.4732, 16.9859, 167.38 and 0.5644 respectively. This indicates varying levels of variability in the distribution with interest cover ratio indicating high variations in the distributions. Similarly, the skewness values obtained as 1.4194, -9.8948, -8.2939 and -6.8435 respectively. The Kurtosis values obtained for these variables were approximately 9.7313, 103.82, 78.21 and 68.72 respectively. Since the values of the kurtosis are greater than zero (0), it indicates a leptokurtic distribution, hence the presence of outliers in the data for the variables.

2. Model evaluation

The suitability of the data was assessed through coefficient and residuals diagnostics. These include normality test, multicollinearity test and heteroscedasticity test.

1. Normality test

Fig. 4.1 Jarque-Bera Normality test results

Source: E-views 10.0 Output (2025)

A significant Jarque-Bera test result implies that the data do not follow a normal distribution. On the other hand, a non-significant result indicates that there is insufficient evidence to reject the assumption of normality. If the p-value associated with the Jarque-Bera test is below a predetermined significance level ($p < 0.05$), then we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the data do not follow a normal distribution. With a p-value of 0.182747, there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the data were normally distributed.

2. Multicollinearity test

In examining the association among the variables, the study employed the Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient (correlation matrix), and the results are as presented in the table below.

Table 4.2 Spearman's rank correlation matrix

	C A S H R D	E R I C R T D R
C A S H R	1.000000	-0.049740 0.265638-0.231569
D E R	-0.049740	1.000000-0.088551 0.716189
I C R	0.265638	-0.088551 1.000000-0.201889
T D R	-0.231569	0.716189-0.201889 1.000000

Source: E-views 10.0 Output (2025)

The correlation analysis showed that all independent variables- Debt-Equity Ratio (DER), Interest Cover Ratio (ICR) and Total Debt Ratio (TDR) of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria over the period under study had coefficients lesser than 0.80 respectively confirming absence of multicollinearity issues.

3. Heteroscedasticity test

Table 4.3 Cross-section dependence/ Heteroscedasticity test

T e s t	Statistic	d . f .	Prob .
Breusch - Pagan LM	82.270566	60	0.0852
Pesaran scaled LM	0.371704		0.7101
Pesaran CD	-0.659022		0.5099

Source: E-views 10.0 Output (2025)

The statistics and probability value associated with the Breusch-Pagan LM test otherwise known as the Breusch-Pagan Godfrey test help determine whether there is evidence of heteroscedasticity in the regression model. A low p-value ($p < 0.05$) suggests evidence against the null hypothesis in favour of the alternate hypothesis which indicates the presence of heteroscedasticity in the regression model. With a p-value of 0.0852, there is sufficient evidence to accept the null hypothesis, thus, conclude that the predictor variables were homoscedastic.

3. Autocorrelation

Autocorrelation tests examine whether the residuals are independently distributed or if there is a systematic pattern of dependence. The Durbin-Watson statistic is commonly used to test for autocorrelation, with values close to 2 indicating no significant autocorrelation. The Durbin-Watson statistic value of 1.760209 suggest a mild positive autocorrelation in the residuals of the regression model.

Test of Hypotheses

Each of the hypotheses in this study was tested based on the result obtained from the panel multiple regression analysis. The result that relates to these hypotheses is summarized in table 4.4 below;

Table 4.4 Panel multiple regression results

Dependent Variable: CASHR
 Method: Panel Least Squares
 Date: 04/10/25 Time: 15:16
 Sample: 2014 2023
 Periods included: 10
 Cross-sections included: 12
 Total panel (balanced) observations: 120

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.441466	0.055201	7.997367	0.0000
DER	-0.002199	0.002547	-3.863351	0.0097
ICR	0.000296	0.000257	1.150370	0.124
TDR	-0.000111	0.076642	-1.541083	0.1260

R-squared	0.038777	Mean dependent var	0.379412
Adjusted R-squared	0.013918	S.D. dependent var	0.473211
S.E. of regression	0.469907	Akaike info criterion	1.360199
Sum squared resid	25.61421	Schwarz criterion	1.453116
Log likelihood	-77.61196	Hannan-Quinn criter.	1.397933
F-statistic	9.559870	Durbin-Watson stat	1.760209
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000915		

Source: Researcher's computation using E-views 10.0 (2025)

The multiple regression line is as written below:

$$CASHR = 0.441465690329 - 0.00219881946272 * DER + 0.000296053154517 * ICR - 0.000111497583 * TDR + \mu$$

Considering the regression results above, when the independent variables- Debt-Equity Ratio (DER), Interest Cover Ratio (ICR) and Total Debt Ratio (TDR) of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria are held constant (equal Zero), the dependent variable- Cash Ratio (CashR) stood at a constant average of approximately 0.4414 (44.14%) over the years. However, a one percent rise in Interest Cover Ratio (ICR) increases cash ratio (CashR) by 0.029% while a similar variation in Debt-Equity Ratio (DER) and Total Debt Ratio (TDR) decreases cash ratio (CashR) by approximately 0.219% and 0.011% respectively.

Hypothesis one

H₀: There is no significant relationship between debt equity ratio and liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria

H₁: There is significant relationship between debt equity ratio and liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria

By way of testing whether the variations in liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria caused by debt equity ratio is significant, T-test was carried out at .05 significance level with T_{tab} of 2.178 given at $T_{0.05,12}$. From the result above, the T_{cal} of 3.863351 is greater than T_{tab} given at $T_{0.05,12}$. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between debt equity ratio and liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria fails to hold, thus rejected, and the alternative hypothesis accepted. The null hypothesis is further rejected given that at $T_{0.05,12}$, its probability value (p-value = 0.0097) is less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$).

Hypothesis two

H₀: There is no significant relationship between interest coverage ratio and liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria

H₁: There is significant relationship between interest coverage ratio and liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria

In respect of interest coverage ratio, the T-test was also employed. From the result above, the T_{cal} of 2.650370 is greater than T_{tab} given at $T_{0.05,12}$. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between interest coverage ratio and cash ratio of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria fails to hold, thus rejected, and the alternative hypothesis accepted. The null hypothesis is further rejected given that at $T_{0.05,12}$, its probability value (p-value = 0.0124) is less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$).

Hypothesis three

H₀: There is no significant relationship between total debt ratio and liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria

H₁: There is significant relationship between total debt ratio and liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria

In addition, the T-test was also employed for total debt ratio. From the result above, the T_{cal} of 1.541083 is less than T_{tab} given at $T_{0.05,12}$. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between total debt ratio and liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria holds, thus accepted, and the alternative hypothesis rejected. The null hypothesis is further accepted given that at $T_{0.05,12}$, its probability value (p-value = 0.1260) is greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$).

Discussion of Findings

Debt equity ratio and liquidity

The study revealed that debt equity ratio has a significant negative relationship with liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria. This suggests that as the debt equity ratio increases, the cash ratio decreases. This implies that firms with higher debt equity ratios tend to have lower cash ratios, indicating a higher reliance on debt financing and a lower ability to meet short-term obligations. This is consistent with the pecking order theory, which suggests that firms prioritize internal financing over external financing, and debt financing is used as a

last resort. Firms with high debt equity ratios may need to reassess their capital structure and consider reducing their reliance on debt financing. Additionally, firms may need to improve their cash management practices to ensure they have sufficient liquidity to meet their short-term obligations. This is in line with the findings of Ofulue et al. (2022), who studied the relationship between financial leverage and financial performance of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Similarly, Odum et al. (2021) examined the effect of financial leverage on financial performance of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

Interest coverage ratio and liquidity

The study also revealed that interest coverage ratio has a significant positive relationship with liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria suggests that as the interest coverage ratio increases, the cash ratio also increases. This implies that firms with higher interest coverage ratios tend to have higher cash ratios, indicating a higher ability to meet interest payments and a lower risk of default. This finding is consistent with the signalling theory, which suggests that firms with higher interest coverage ratios are perceived as less risky and more creditworthy. The positive relationship between interest coverage ratio and cash ratio has significant implications for firms' financial management and risk assessment. Firms with high interest coverage ratios may be viewed as more creditworthy and may have better access to debt financing. This result agrees with the discoveries of Kenn-Ndubisi et al., (2019).

Total debt ratio and liquidity

In addition, total debt ratio has a non-significant negative relationship with liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria suggests that there is no statistically significant relationship between total debt ratio and liquidity. This implies that the total debt ratio does not have a significant impact on the cash ratio of firms in the sample. This finding may be due to the fact that firms in the sample may be using debt financing for different purposes, such as investing in profitable projects or financing working capital. The non-significant relationship between total debt ratio and liquidity has implications for firms' financial management and capital structure decisions. Firms need to consider other factors, such as interest coverage ratio and debt equity ratio, when making decisions about their capital structure. This aligns with the position of Mwangi and Simiyu, (2024) and that of Ofulue et al. (2022).

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of the Findings

The data collected were analysed using panel simple regression technique. Based on the analysis of data collected, the following findings were drawn:

- [1] Debt equity ratio has a significant negative relationship (Coeff. = -0.00219{0.0097}) with liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria.
- [2] Interest coverage ratio has a significant positive relationship (Coeff. = 0.00029{0.0124}) with liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria.
- [3] Total debt ratio has a non-significant negative relationship (Coeff. = -0.00011{0.1260}) with liquidity of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

Conclusion

This study examined the relationship between financial leverage and financial stability of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The findings of this study contribute to the existing body of knowledge on the impact of financial leverage on the financial stability of firms. The study's outcomes have important implications for stakeholders, including investors, creditors, and managers of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The study suggests that financial leverage have a significant impact on the financial stability of firms, and therefore, firms should carefully manage their debt levels to ensure financial stability. The study's findings also highlight the need for policymakers and regulators to put in place effective regulations to guide the use of debt financing by firms in Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are footprints of the study findings

1. To mitigate the negative impact of debt equity ratio on liquidity, quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria should consider reducing their debt levels and increasing their equity base. This could be achieved through strategies such as debt restructuring, equity financing, and improving profitability to reduce dependence on debt.
2. Given the significant positive relationship between interest coverage ratio and liquidity, quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria should prioritize improving their interest coverage ratio. This could be achieved by increasing profitability, reducing interest expenses, and optimizing debt financing costs.
3. Although the total debt ratio has a non-significant negative relationship with liquidity, quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria should still exercise caution when using debt financing. Firms should regularly review their debt levels and ensure that they are within manageable limits to avoid potential liquidity and solvency issues.

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